

Chromaticity Specification

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ABSTRACT. A specification for the chromaticity of the Gaia Astro instrument is proposed, including new definitions (for this specific purpose only!) of the image centroid and the chromatic displacement. It also includes a specific recipe for estimating the residual chromatic effect after field-averaging, calibration, and propagation to the final astrometric data.

1 Introduction

‘Chromaticity’ is a general term referring to several related phenomena:

- that the measured centre (however that is defined) of a monochromatic stellar image is wavelength dependent due to diffraction;
- that the corresponding centre of a polychromatic image therefore depends on the stellar spectrum;
- that the calibration of these shifts is imperfect and therefore adds noise to the observations; and
- that this noise propagates to the final astrometric results.

The actual error propagation is extremely complicated, and depends on many factors that are only partially known at the present, such as details of the calibration and centroiding procedures, and the photometric bands available. In order to arrive at a practically useful specification it is therefore necessary to adopt a much simplified error model, with conservative assumptions on the most critical (or least known) steps.

Gai et al. (CWG-GAI-001, 6 Nov 2003) analyzed the relative displacements of monochromatic images separately for different terms of the optical aberrations (expanded in Zernike or Fringe Zernike polynomials) and identified the critical terms. Not surprisingly, these turn out to be the odd parity terms (except the tilt term, which of course gives an achromatic shift). It was also noted that, for the nominal instrument (i.e., without alignment and polishing errors), the critical terms are anti-symmetric with respect to the along-scan field coordinate, so that there is a high degree of compensation at transit level. A conclusion from the work may be that emphasis should be put on minimizing the odd parity terms of WFE, and that the (partial) compensation at transit level should be taken advantage of.

While CWG–GAI–001 gives a very useful indication of the criticality of different WFE shapes, it does not provide a specification of what might constitute an acceptable WFE. Indeed, it is probably desirable to formulate the chromaticity specification not in terms of the WFE, but rather directly in terms of the acceptable chromatic shift, suitably defined and based on a very simplified error propagation model.

It is the purpose of this note to propose such a rough model. It includes in particular: (i) a practical definition of what should be considered the (along-scan) ‘centre’ of an optical image or LSF; (ii) a practical quantification of chromaticity on the image level; (iii) an assumption concerning the efficiency of the chromaticity calibration procedure; (iv) consideration of the efficiency of FOV averaging; (v) a recipe for the propagation of residual chromaticity to the astrometric results; and (vi) a specification of the acceptable level of contribution to the astrometry. Each of these items is addressed below.

2 Definition of image centre

An algorithm for centroiding on noisy CCD sample data in Astro has been described e.g. in SAG–LL–032 (4 Oct 2000). Briefly, it makes a maximum-likelihood (ML) fit of a calibrated line-spread function (LSF) to the observed data. However, that (or similar) centroiding algorithms are not useful for the present purpose, chiefly because they require sampled data as input, and effectively uses a different centroid definition for every observation (e.g., as function of the colour or noise level). What we need is a simple way to define the centroid of a continuous, noise-free LSF, which still is in some sense ‘realistic’ relative to an algorithm such as the one in SAG–LL–032. For instance, one important feature of any realistic centroid definition must be that it only uses the central part of the LSF, corresponding to some 5 or 6 along-scan samples.

Let us first define exactly what we mean by the LSF, denoted $L(u)$, where u is the one-dimensional along-scan coordinate measured in pixels from some arbitrary origin (cf. GAIA-LL-046). We define $L(u)$ by specifying the specific steps by which it may be calculated:

1. The monochromatic optical LSF $L_\lambda^O(u)$ is obtained as the squared modulus of the Fourier transform of the complex pupil function (including WFE), or equivalently as the Fourier transform of the optical transfer function (the autocorrelation of the pupil function). It is a complete LSF, i.e. the truncation by the finite sample size across-scan is not considered.
2. The optical LSF is convolved with three rectangular functions representing the along-scan pixel width ($\Delta u = 1$ pixel), the motion of the optical image during one along-scan charge transfer phase ($\Delta u = 1/4$ pixel for a four-phase CCD), and the total shift of the optical image with respect to the charge image over the CCD integration time due to rate error and distortion gradient (some fraction of a pixel). The resulting monochromatic total LSF is denoted $L_\lambda(u)$.
3. The polychromatic total LSF $L(u)$ is obtained as the photoelectron-weighted mean of $L_\lambda(u)$.

The proposed definition of the centroid coordinate u_0 is:

$$\sum_{k=-2}^2 w_k L(u_0 + k) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where $(w_{-2}, w_{-1}, w_0, w_{+1}, w_{+2}) = (-0.6, -1.0, 0, +1.0, +0.6)$ is a set of fixed weights chosen to approximate the sensitivity of the ML algorithm to the different parts of the LSF.

3 Definition of chromatic displacement

Numerical experiments with the centroid definition in (1) applied to various polychromatic images with different WFE leads to the conclusion that the centroid of a polychromatic LSF is approximately given by the monochromatic centroid at the effective wavelength

$$\bar{\lambda} = \frac{\int N_\lambda d\lambda}{\int \lambda^{-1} N_\lambda d\lambda} \quad (2)$$

where N_λ is the spectrum of photoelectrons per unit wavelength. With current data for the optical transmittance (Ag^6) and quantum efficiency of the AF we have $\bar{\lambda} \simeq 580$ nm for a hot star (spectral type B0) and $\simeq 800$ nm for a cool star (M8). We may consider these to represent the most extreme colours for normal (unreddened) stars.

Thus we define the ‘chromatic displacement’ as the difference between the monochromatic centroids at these wavelengths:

$$\Delta u = (u_0 \text{ for } L_{800 \text{ nm}}) - (u_0 \text{ for } L_{580 \text{ nm}}) \quad (3)$$

4 Efficiency of chromaticity calibration

The accuracy by which the polychromatic centroid position can be predicted for an object with an arbitrary spectrum, using a linear regression model versus the BBP fluxes, was studied in GAIA–LL–049 for some representative BBP filter systems. The prediction error is (understandably) much smaller for objects with ‘normal’ stellar spectra than e.g. for emission-line objects such as quasars. For instance, the RMS prediction error for the filter system depicted in Fig. 3b of that note was about 8 times larger for quasars than for normal stars. Computing the chromatic displacement according to (3) for the different WFE maps considered in GAIA–LL–049, it was found that the prediction error for a given class of objects and for a given filter system was approximately proportional to Δu . For normal stars, the constant of proportionality ranges from 0.2% (filter system 2e) to 0.9% (system 4b), and for quasars from 0.8% (2e) to 3.6% (4b). Considering that actual stars have a larger spread in spectral distributions than assumed in that study, it would not be safe to assume a smaller calibration error than 1% of the chromatic displacement. Therefore, let us assume that the RMS chromaticity error after calibration is

$$\sigma_u = 0.01 |\Delta u| \quad (4)$$

However, this formula is not directly used in the specification below, because we also need to consider field averaging.

5 Field averaging

Equation (4) refers to the RMS residual error in whatever part of the AF where an *independent* chromaticity calibration is made. In practice the residual errors may be strongly correlated (or anti-correlated) between such areas because the WFE map changes only gradually with field position. In particular, if Δu is an anti-symmetric (odd) function of the AL field coordinate η (e.g., $\Delta u = C(\eta - \eta_0)$, where C is a constant and η_0 the AL centre of the AF), then one can assume that the residual errors to a large extent cancel over a FOV transit (cf. CWG–GAI–001). The specification should take into account such compensational behaviour, at the same time as one should not rely overly on the cancellation of very large shifts. A reasonable compromise is suggested below in Eq. (9).

Let $\Delta u(\eta, \zeta)$ be the chromaticity map in the AF (one of the viewing directions). Let η_{\min} , η_{\max} , etc., denote the extreme coordinates of the AF. For any AC coordinate ζ we define the AL-averaged chromaticity as

$$\langle \Delta u \rangle_{\text{AL}}(\zeta) = \frac{1}{\eta_{\max} - \eta_{\min}} \int_{\eta_{\min}}^{\eta_{\max}} \Delta u(\eta, \zeta) d\eta \quad (5)$$

and the field-averaged chromaticity as

$$\langle \Delta u \rangle = \frac{1}{\zeta_{\max} - \zeta_{\min}} \int_{\zeta_{\min}}^{\zeta_{\max}} \langle \Delta u \rangle_{\text{AL}}(\zeta) d\zeta \quad (6)$$

The RMS AL-averaged chromaticity is then

$$[\langle \Delta u \rangle_{\text{AL}}]_{\text{RMS}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\zeta_{\max} - \zeta_{\min}} \int_{\zeta_{\min}}^{\zeta_{\max}} [\langle \Delta u \rangle_{\text{AL}}(\zeta)]^2 d\zeta} \quad (7)$$

We also need the total chromaticity dispersion,

$$[\Delta u]_{\text{D}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{(\eta_{\max} - \eta_{\min})(\zeta_{\max} - \zeta_{\min})} \int_{\eta_{\min}}^{\eta_{\max}} \int_{\zeta_{\min}}^{\zeta_{\max}} [\Delta u(\eta, \zeta) - \langle \Delta u \rangle]^2 d\eta d\zeta} \quad (8)$$

It is understood that the integrals in Eqs. (5)–(8) in practice have to be evaluated as weighted sums over a finite number of field points.

The RMS residual chromaticity for a single transit is now estimated by the following formula, replacing Eq. (4):

$$\sigma_u = 0.01 \sqrt{[\langle \Delta u \rangle_{\text{AL}}]_{\text{RMS}}^2 + ([\Delta u]_{\text{D}}/4)^2} \quad (9)$$

The factor 4 in the second term is somewhat arbitrary, but gives a reasonable limit on the degree to which we may rely on cancellation in the AL anti-symmetric part of Δu . For instance, a constant chromaticity of 490 μas over the whole field is just acceptable according to (9)–(11), but so is a chromaticity that varies linearly with η and having a maximum of $\pm 3396 \mu\text{as}$ at the edges of the AF. On the other hand, if the chromaticity varies linearly with the AC coordinate ζ , then the maximum acceptable amplitude would only be $\pm 824 \mu\text{as}$.

6 Propagation of residual chromaticity to astrometry

Since (9) refers to a single FOV transit, and each transit can be considered independent, the final step of the propagation to the parallax is the same as for (transit-averaged) photon-statistical errors, viz.:

$$\sigma_\pi = 0.204\sigma_u \quad (10)$$

where we adopt the average coefficient of improvement $\langle \text{COI}_\pi \rangle = 0.204$ from Gaia-JdB-012.

7 Specification of the contribution to the parallax error

The contribution of chromaticity to the parallax of a (bright) star should be at most 1 micro-arcsec:

$$\sigma_\pi \leq 1 \mu\text{as} \quad (11)$$

8 Final remark

This specification does not put any limit at all on the total WFE, only (implicitly) on the anti-symmetric terms that contribute to the chromaticity. Other (symmetric) terms cause a broadening of the LSF which degrades the astrometric performance, but it is assumed that this is effectively covered by other specifications.